

AUTHOR**Azimov Yusufjon**

*Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston
Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali katta
o'qituvchisi.*

Azimov Yusufjon

*Senior lecturer of the Jizzakh branch of the
National University of Uzbekistan named
after Mirzo Ulugbek.*

АЗИМОВ ЮСУФЖОН

*Старший преподаватель Джизакского
филиала Национального университета
Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека.*

Email:azimovyusuf@jbnuu.uz**©2024. Azimov Yusufjon.****TA'LIM JARAYONIDA KREATIVLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH****DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVISM IN THE
EDUCATIONAL PROCESS****РАЗВИТИЕ КРЕАТИВНОСТИ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ
ПРОЦЕССЕ****ANNOTATSIIYA**

Maqolada fizika darslarida kompetensiyasilarni shakllantirishning kreativ o'qitish jarayonidagi turli jihatlarini ko'rib chiqilgan.

ANNOTATION

The article examines various aspects of the formation of competencies in physics lessons in the process of creative teaching.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассмотрены различные аспекты формирования компетенций на уроках физики в процессе творческого обучения.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

kompetensiyasilarni shakllantirish, ta'lim sifati, kompetentlik, kompetensiyaviy yondoshuv, kreativ, ta'lim, ta'lim jarayoni, o'quvchilar.

KEYWORDS

formation of competencies, quality of Education, competence, competency approach, creative, educational, educational process, students.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

формирование компетенций, качество образования, компетентность, компетентностный подход, креатив, образование, учебный процесс, учащиеся.

Introduction

The current rapidly changing technique and technology has come to many countries around the world in recent times, demanding the further development of creativity (creativity) in the process of school education with the help of certain creative styles. These countries are trying to compensate for the community's order for creative ideas by introducing into the educational process various activities aimed at the development of the educational system creativism (creativity). They realize that the introduction of the basics of creative pedagogy into the educational process is a more effective measure, aimed at specific innovative and creative activities capable of systematically forming, developing and adapting the skills of creative thinking of the student's personality.

Based on the goal of developing students' creative thinking, the governments of all world countries are setting new tasks for their educational systems. For example, as of 2009, the UK education system declared that the main goal of school education is to transform the country into a "world center of creativity" by introducing pedagogical technologies that have been successfully tested in educational processes, serving to form and develop effective thinking of students.

MAIN PART

Formation of creativity for all students based on high goals a program of actions is being developed, one of the main rules in the program is aimed at developing imagination, purposefulness of actions and self-identification, creativity and perception are not juxtaposed, but complement each other side by side, enriching the content of the educational process, it considers important opportunities for A.Maslow's views. [1]

In educational institutions of our country, it is important to educate a mature person who is able to think creatively, fighting against the speed and tension of the modern world, where students should receive knowledge aimed at comprehensively developing their creative

abilities, develop communication skills and creative thinking, focus on creating all the conditions for obtaining knowledge in free conditions, become one of the most.

When organizing creative education for high schools, it is necessary to create a desire to seek knowledge in each student, focusing on the development of creative thinking of all students, generating motivational factors that motivate them to think creatively. To create such a situation, in the course of the lesson, it is required to form a sense of innovation, providing students with free movement. The main task of the teacher in the course of the lesson is to create motivational conditions for the creative fixation of his students. Classroom and extracurricular technologies that encourage creative activity increase students' motivation to develop creative thinking, indicating their greater satisfaction with the learning process. The effectiveness of creative thinking decreases if creative methods are used as a reward or as a distraction from a lesson. Misuse or insufficient use of creative ideas in the course of the lesson, selective use does not give the expected effectiveness. [2]

The teacher is required to provide in the course of the lesson developing tasks using a certain methodological base, conceptual developing tasks, tasks for developing creative thinking skills, in which a certain technique of creative teaching is applied in practice, and tasks that can be used for the independent work of students. The teacher and student's creative thinking should be interpreted as any action that leads to the development of new creative thinking, considered as a complex of special abilities, motivations, habits and circumstances inherent in any individual, especially felt in "gifted" individuals. In this case, creativity is defined as the process of creating a new integrity by converting existing elements into a new form.

During the course of the lesson, the teacher is required to discuss and give examples of innovations in physics together with students. Dozens of innovations in physics and what physical law they work according to are justified

in the discussion process. In such an organization of the course process, even in the format of a long-minute lesson, the attention of students does not fade. Some ideas can be expressed about the creative methodology of the teacher in the course of the lesson:

- the constant state of joy of the student arises, supported by the feeling of striving for deep knowledge of physics;
- with the teacher's stimulating tone of voice and elegant body language, students' fear and shyness disappear;
- students' creative thinking skills are controlled;
- each student is given the opportunity to express their opinion independently;
- the wrong answer of the student is not suppressed by the teacher, but directed to a more acceptable option;
- in the course of the lesson, an atmosphere of mutual trust and cooperation occurs. The hope arises to increase the mandatory knowledge in other disciplines, which are adjacent to science;
- the opportunity arises to take a personal approach to each student;
- the possibility of a good organization of the course process occurs;
- the individual response of the reader requires the use of elements of the game "following the leader" to help get rid of tension and shyness;
- the possibility of making the most of the entire space of the classroom occurs;
- effectively used the mood of students and their level of knowledge in science.

From the above, it can be said that they show several areas of effective work to develop students' creative thinking:

1. As much as possible, it will be necessary to give students the opportunity to choose when completing the task.
2. Encourage and use the project as a way for students to strengthen positive emotions, but this should not remain the sole purpose of the project.

3. In the course of the lesson, it is required to keep the game and fantastic moments in the correct context.

4. Maintain sufficient emotional distance in relationships with students and should be treated with warmth and support, but give students the opportunity to be independent and proactive.

5. Take an impartial approach to helping students constructively assess their independent work, but don't abuse the assessment method.

6. Encourage students and encourage them to make unusual decisions.

7. Help students resist pressure and obey general rules only for obedience [4].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the main factor in the development of creative thinking is motivation, which is manifested in a strong interest and perseverance in identifying vague and unknown things, as well as in the development of alternative, most promising things, interest in finding specific searches for solving problems. scenarios consist of information search, technological and subject-oriented cognitive abilities, and communication. The teacher plays a key role in increasing the creative thinking potential of students. This situation can occur in the process of mastering traditional curricula. Most importantly, the teacher should be prepared for such a lesson process, understand the connection between creative education and personal value directions, and stimulate the motivation of students to independently carry out educational tasks, effectively reconnecting.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Кундозерова Л.И., Бойченко Г.Н. Теория обучения. Педагогические технологии: учебное пособие / д-р пед. наук, проф. Л.И.Кундозерова; канд. пед. наук, доц. Г.Н.Бойченко. - Новокузнецк: ФКОУ ВО Кузбасский институт ФСИИ России, 2017. – 83 с.
2. Закиева А., Лушпаева И., Проектирование урока в современных условиях .[Электронный

ресурс]: URL:<http://magarif-uku.ru/proektirovanie-uroka-v-sovremennykh->
u/

3. Стандарты второго поколения, Просвещение. [Электронный ресурс]: URL:
<http://prosv.ru/attachment.aspx?id=23395>

4. Сериков В.В. Развитие личности в образовательном процессе / В. В. Сериков. — Москва: Логос, 2012. — 447 с.

